

Kinetics of the Leaching Process of Clay Minerals in Acid and Alkali Medium

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Manuscript received 14 February 1985, revised 17 March 1986, accepted 12 August 1986

The kinetics of clay-aqueous phase interaction has been studied taking kaolinitic and montmorillonitic (bentonite) clay minerals of Indian origin. The leaching agents used were acid and alkali. The decomposition appeared to be controlled by the equation $Q^{\circ} = K/T$. The gradual breakdown of the clay structure has been interpreted through the curves obtained by plotting change of molar ratio of $Al_2O_3 - SiO_2$ as a function of time.

THE study of the kinetics of the decomposition of clay minerals in various chemical agents in aqueous solution is important because it reflects some of the characteristic features of the structure of clay minerals. From the practical point of view, this study gives an idea about the utilisation of various clay minerals as source of aluminium and its compounds, fixation of certain materials like phosphate in soils, and resistivity towards chemical agents.

The mechanism of vigorous attack by acids has been studied by X-ray method. Glasser¹ and Mering² have shown that 75 to 85% of the total alumina must be lost before complete disruption of the lattice occurs. The clay can be reconstituted if appropriate bases are added before X-ray pattern disappears. Dissolution of octahedral layers thus apparently occurs progressively from the outer edges. Support for this concept is afforded by the rate of dissolution experiments by Brindley and Youell³ on chlorites and by those of Osthans⁴ on nontronite and montmorillonite. Such studies make it possible to determine by chemical means the metallic ions present in tetrahedral and octahedral coordination. Gastuche and Fripiat⁵ found that the differential attack on the octahedral layers as compared with tetrahedral layers was improved by using solution of acid saturated with silica.

Kinetics of reaction of HCl with kaolinite were studied by Gastuche *et al.*⁶ over a range of pH and temperatures and the products were examined by electron microscope and X-rays. The reaction proceeded in such a way that the crystallites were attacked uniformly in all directions. The activation energies for dissolution of $SiO_2 - Al_2O_3$ cracking catalyst and silica gel were approximately equal ($18 - 20 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$), indicating that the destruction of silicic parts of the structure was the rate determining process, the removal of surface aluminium being very rapid. Osthans⁷ found that the dissolution of ions from the lattice of montmorillonites was in agreement with chemical kinetics and was a

first order reaction. The rate constant for the acid-solution increased proportionately with the acid concentration. Activation energies for single samples of montmorillonite and nontronite were $17 - 18 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ in both the cases. The applicability of equilibrium relationship to the mobility of aluminium and silica in open system (soil columns) was examined by Marion *et al.*⁸ in nine soils representing six soil orders. They concluded that the applicability of equilibrium concepts to open-systems depended on the reaction rate and residence time; the reaction rate being controlled by mineral solubility, chemical composition of the medium, temperature, degree of mixing and mineral surface area exposed. Langston and Jenne⁹ determined total alumina and silica contents of the kaolinite-2 and -7 by decomposing 50-75 mg of clay with 10 ml of 15% NaOH in a platinum crucible through evaporation, followed by heating to a dull heat for 20-30 min and cooling with the solids being taken up in 20 ml of 1:1 HCl (overnight) and diluted to 1000 ml. The authors concluded that the decomposition rate of kaolinite-2 was much slower than that of kaolinite-7.

In the present investigation, the kinetics of the decomposition of purified kaolinite and bentonite in aqueous, acidic and alkaline phases were studied to throw some light on the mechanism of the decomposition process.

Experimental

Rajmahal chinaclay and Tinpahari bentonite of Indian origin were selected for the present investigation because of a high proportion of kaolinite and montmorillonite, respectively, in these clays. The raw clays were purified from the associated impurities in the following way. The raw clay (~1 kg) was first blunged in a large volume of water in a glass jar (10 dm³). After proper shaking, the suspension was thoroughly stirred with addition of

deflocculant (sodium hexametaphosphate, 0.002 g dm⁻³). The clay layer at the top was carefully separated into another jar and this operation was repeated to remove non-clay material as long as it was visible at the bottom of the jar. Then the clay was just flocculated with HCl. After siphoning the clear supernatant liquid, H₂O₂ (50 ml of 20% per 2 dm³ suspension) was added to decompose organic matter. This was repeated until effervescence ceased. It was then subjected to repeated leaching treatment with 0.01 N HCl to remove acid-soluble impurities. The excess acid was removed by settling under a large volume of water as described above. The kaolinite and bentonite thus purified were converted to Na-form by treatment with 0.25 M NaCl, the excess of which removed by the same procedure. The Na-clay was filtered, then washed with water until free from chloride. Bentonite was coagulated with a mixture of ethanol-water (80 : 20) during washing. Finally, they were dialysed in a large volume of water, dried, ground to powder and kept in a constant temperature incubator (36±1°).

For the purpose of leaching¹⁰ clay (1 g) was treated with the leaching agent (acid or alkali) (50 ml) in a clean dry conical flask (100 ml). The mouth of the flask was covered with tin foil in order to avoid evaporation. After gentle swirling,

the flasks were clamped in a water-bath. After a specified time at a fixed temperature, the flasks were cooled to room temperature and filtered under suction through Whatman no. 40 filter paper, washed with distilled water, and the volume of filtrate made upto 250 ml. The silica and alumina in the leached liquid were analysed colorimetrically¹¹ and complexometrically¹², respectively.

Results and Discussion

Purified kaolinite and bentonite in sodium-form were taken for the present investigation. The leaching operation was carried out in a closed system and then the aqueous phase was separated. The constituents leached out in aqueous phase were analysed as a function of time. The extent to which the solids dissolve in liquids varies greatly with the nature of solid and liquid, the temperature and to a much lesser degree with the pressure on the system. The total solubility as well as those of individual constituents when plotted against time exhibited parabolic curves with no discontinuity. Because of the similar nature some of the representative curves are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The nature of the curves was independent of the nature of the clay minerals as well as the leaching agent. Again for comparative study log (solubility) was plotted

Fig. 1. Isothermal solubility curves of Na-kaolinite in different concentrations of H₂SO₄ and NaOH : (x) 30, (●) 50, (Δ) 75 and (○) 98°.

Fig. 2. Isothermal leaching rate curves of SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 from Na-kaolinite: (x) 30, (●) 50, (Δ) 75 and (○) 98°.

Fig. 3. Leaching rate curves of Na-kaolinite with respect to total solubility: (●) 30, (●) 50, (Δ) 75 and (○) 98°.

against log (time) and one representative is shown in Fig. 3. The major portion of the curves exhibited straight line relationship which followed the equation $Q^a = KT$, where Q is the amount of material extracted from the clay structure in time T , and a and K are constants. From the log—log plot of solubility, the value of a for the individual constituents were calculated and are given in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—CALCULATED VALUES OF a FOR TOTAL SOLUBILITY OF CLAYS DURING LEACHING WITH ACID AND ALKALI

Concn. N	Temp. °C	Na-Kaolinite		Na-Bentonite	
		H ₂ SO ₄	NaOH	H ₂ SO ₄	NaOH
0.2	98	2.508	5.640	3.763	7.080
	75	6.021	3.950	5.016	7.525
	50	6.021	6.770	5.016	7.525
	30	7.525	7.520	7.525	10.080
0.1	98	2.867	7.770	5.016	6.020
	75	6.021	7.525	5.016	7.250
	50	7.525	8.050	7.525	7.250
	30	10.210	7.525	5.016	15.050
0.04	98	7.525	5.016	7.525	15.050
	75	6.021	6.020	7.525	10.080
	50	6.690	7.525	7.525	10.080
	30	7.525	7.525	5.016	7.250
0.02	98	5.017	6.730	7.525	
	75	5.017	7.525	6.020	
	50	6.021	7.820	7.525	
	30	6.690	7.120	7.525	

TABLE 2—CALCULATED VALUES OF a OF EACH CONSTITUENT OF CLAYS DURING LEACHING WITH H₂SO₄

Concn. of H ₂ SO ₄ N	Temp. °C	Na-Kaolinite		Na-Bentonite	
		SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃
0.2	98	2.84	1.80	5.68	1.91
	75	2.98	2.82	7.57	2.02
	50	5.26	6.02	9.56	2.10
	30	6.66	6.45	9.90	1.62
0.1	98	4.08	1.50	6.66	2.10
	75	6.02	3.01	7.81	2.26
	50	7.04	3.77	9.52	4.31
	30	10.63	4.52	11.62	1.92

From the above studies it appears that the values of a were to a great extent an inverse function of temperature of reaction in the case of higher concentration of leaching agents, whereas at lower concentrations, there was minor variation in the values of a with decrease in temperature. Thermal agitation increased the kinetic energy of diffusing ions and also partially or completely removed the deposited insoluble layer from the surface of the particles; thus maintaining a more or less constant concentration gradient. This was observed from the fact that the value of a at 98° and at high concentration was nearly 2.0. It is to be noted here that the value of a was greater than 2.0, indicating very slow reaction rate. This might be due to the fact that the concentration gradient was not constant, particularly during leaching at low tempera-

ture, at low concentration and the composition of the aqueous phase continuously changed with time in this closed system of study. Moreover, the nature and the amount of deposited material were found to influence the reaction to a great extent. If the concentration gradient remains constant, the value of a would be 2.0. From the above curves it appears that (i) the rate of dissolution of alumina was high compared to that of silica for both the clays which might be related to the reaction affinity of the former with leaching agent and (ii) the rate was found to be directly related to the concentration of the leaching agent and the temperature of the reaction. In general, the rate of dissolution of kaolinite was found to be greater than that of bentonite, the difference being significant in alkaline medium. It is to be noted that the rate of dissolution of bentonite was found to be greater than that of kaolinite in case of alkali medium at 0.2 and 0.04 N and also in acid medium at 0.1 and 0.02 N . When the total solubility was considered, the same type of relationship was observed as with the individual constituents. Alumina and silica are the main structural constituents of clay minerals. In the rate study the change of molar ratio of Al₂O₃—SiO₂ in the aqueous phase gave an indication as to how the structure was affected. This value was calculated as a function of time for each concentration at different temperatures (Fig. 4). From Fig. 4 it appears that the molar ratio (Al₂O₃—SiO₂) gradually increases with time at all concentration for both the clays. Slight deviation was observed in case of kaolinite during leaching with H₂SO₄ when the ratio was found to decrease after 480 min although the initial path was similar. The change of molar ratio with time followed a more or less a parallel curve. For kaolinite the value of molar ratio never exceeded that present in the original sample. But for bentonite it exceeded the latter at 0.2 N H₂SO₄ concentration and at higher temperature. The nature of curve remained more or less same for both the clays although the magnitude differed. In acid medium at low concentration and at low temperature, the change of molar ratio was significantly low compared to other cases. Thus the temperature and concentration played an important role with respect to the change of molar ratio. From the change of molar ratio with time in the leaching process, it appears that the reaction was initiated through the attack of silicate bonds which are comparatively weak. The nature and the amount of insoluble reaction products deposited on the surface as well as the composition of the leaching agent determine the rate of corrosion at this stage.

In the closed batchwise system the products of reaction played an important role in controlling the rate of reaction. In the case of acid and alkali dissolution there was every possibility of formation of insoluble reaction product and the thickness of that layer will determine the rate of reaction. The nature of the dissolution curves reveals that it was mostly a diffusion-controlled process.

Fig. 4. Change of molar ratio $Al_2O_3 : SiO_2$ of Na-kaolinite with time during leaching with H_2SO_4 : (x) 30, (●) 50, (Δ) 75 and (○) 98°.

Conclusion : (i) The mechanism of migration of different constituents from the clay structure during leaching in the aqueous phase remain more or less same irrespective of the nature of the mineral. (ii) The magnitude of solubility was different depending on the intensity of the interaction. (iii) Decomposition of clay minerals in aqueous phase was controlled by the simple equation, $Q^* = KT$. The rate of dissolution of Al_2O_3 was higher than silica for both the cases. (iv) The solubility rate was directly related to the concentration of the leaching agents present as well as the temperature.

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